

Insertion loss prediction of sonic crystal noise barriers covered by porous concrete using the Method of Fundamental Solutions

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Abstract

Noise attenuation by sonic crystal noise barriers occurs mainly in specific frequency bands (bandgaps), due to a mechanism called Bragg scattering, which is the result of destructive interference between multiple reflections. To improve their performance, sound-absorbing materials may be used to coat the rigid scatterers, increasing attenuation in other frequency bands. In this work, the Method of Fundamental Solutions (MFS) is used to evaluate the performance of sonic crystal noise barriers with cylinders covered by porous and granular materials simulating the volume of the absorbent material using equivalent fluid models for porous or granular materials. The proposed numerical models were validated by experimental tests and, afterwards, these numerical models were verified through the comparison with results obtained using the Finite Element Method (FEM). Finally, several numerical tests were performed in order to understand/predict the acoustic behavior of the sonic crystal noise barriers covered with porous concrete.

Keywords: Sonic crystal acoustic barriers, MFS, Numerical model, Equivalent fluid model, Porous concrete.

1. Introduction

Acoustic barriers are a common noise mitigation strategy near residential areas that are located next to roads and are subject to high sound pressure levels. According to Gill [1], Hutchin et al. [2] and Bies et al. [3], the most convenient shape of an acoustic barrier is of the wall type, as it only has diffraction at the top of the barrier, since its length is considered as infinite in relation to its height. The acoustic effectiveness of noise barriers is quantified by the descriptor called “insertion loss” (D_{IL}) which is determined from an in-situ measurement according to the ISO 10847 standard [4].

According to [5, 6, 7, 8], the interest in developing solutions such as sonic crystal barriers has increased for road traffic noise mitigation, as they do not have the problems of reducing the field of vision, daylight, and airflow as traditional acoustic barriers. In 1995, Martínez-Sala et al. [9] proved that the periodic distribution of scatterers in three-dimensional spaces provides sound waves attenuation at specific frequency bands, forming the so-called acoustic bandgaps.

*Fully documented templates are available in the elsarticle package on CTAN.

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According to EN 1793-3 standard [10], the most relevant part of the spectrum is the one close to the third-octave band with a center frequency at 1000 Hz, making it necessary to seek solutions that can be effective for this frequency range. Morandi et al. [11] showed that for a sonic crystal noise barrier with its elements geometrically distributed in a square lattice, the increase in the number of columns in the barrier causes a rise in insertion loss. However, the authors observed that, after the fourth column of elements, there is no longer a significant increase in sound attenuation. Godinho et al. [12] corroborate the idea of "saturation" from the fourth column of sonic crystal elements.

Besides having good efficiency when used for the control of road traffic noise, the sonic crystal noise barriers can also be implemented considering a sustainable feature. Godinho et al. [6] and Amado Mendes et al. [7, 8] studied the use of wood logs from forest cleaning operations as elements of sonic crystals noise barrier.

An interesting way to increase the performance of a noise barrier is to use materials with considerable sound absorption. In Fujiwara et al. [13], it is shown that the attenuation caused by the use of absorbent materials in conjunction with acoustic wall-type barriers can be up to 8 dB. In the case of sonic crystal noise barriers, the work by Umnova et al. [14] presents a study of the acoustic transmission loss of a finite periodic arrangement of long rigid cylinders, with and without porous absorbent coating, [which is studied theoretically with multiple scattering technique and compared with the laboratory measurements](#). The authors predicted that the results are very sensitive to coating material thickness and effective flow resistivity. Furthermore, a random covered array is also predicted to provide better attenuation than a random array of rigid cylinders with the same overall radius and volume fraction.

When a sound absorption treatment is required, the use of porous materials stands out in relation to the use of other materials. Materials such as fibers and foams are commonly used in commercial solutions due to their excellent sound absorption coefficient at high frequencies. However, for external applications, these materials require protection against environmental agents and structural reinforcement. Due to these problems, an alternative to fibers and foams is the use of granular absorbent materials, such as porous concrete. The works of Vašina et al. [15], Asdrubali and Horoshenkov [16] and Carbajo et al. [17] are of great relevance, as they present some values for the macroscopic parameters for concrete materials based on expanded clay.

Pereira et al. [18] studied the sound absorptive behavior of porous concrete samples made using expanded clay aggregates. They analyzed different parameters such as the influence of the grain size, the thickness and the water-cement ratio in the sound absorption coefficient. In addition, Pereira et al [19] presented the Metaporous Concrete concept, where acoustic resonators were embedded in porous concrete samples. This study was performed using the equivalent-fluid theory to represent each part that composes this solution using finite element models.

The present work aims to propose the use of porous concrete materials coating the sonic crystal noise barriers. Thus, it is necessary to develop capable numerical models to predict the performance of these solutions.

A challenge in the analysis of sonic crystals is related to its correct and precise modeling using numerical techniques. More general numerical methods, such as the Finite Difference Time Domain method (FDTD) [20] or the Boundary Element Method (BEM) [21, 22] have been used to calculate the band structure of different sonic crystal configurations. A promising approach using the BEM was presented by Karimi et al. [23], implementing what the authors call Periodic BEM to analyze large matrices of acoustic scatterers periodically distributed. The

Finite Element Method (FEM) has also been used, for example, in defining an engineering approach to the sonic crystal barrier design, using overlapping two-dimensional FEM models [24].

In this work, the Method of Fundamental Solutions (MFS) will be applied to predict the behavior of sonic crystal noise barriers covered by porous materials, being this numerical method a technique without a standard discretization of the domain or its boundaries. Instead of this discretization, the MFS only requires defining a set of points along with the physical limits of the problem. From these points and using a linear combination of the differential equation's fundamental solutions that govern the problem, an approximate solution for the problem is constructed.

The MFS can be found in several works over the past two decades. Noteworthy are the early works of Fairweather and Karageorghis [25], Fairweather et al [26]. and Golberg and Chen [27]. Despite the simplicity of the method, several works already published indicate that it can provide the calculation of very rigorous solutions for different types of physical problems.

Considering the problems of sonic crystal noise barriers, its approach using the FEM would be very laborious, as it requires the discretization of the entire domain. In the case of the BEM, it would require a higher computational cost and the resolution of several integrals along the boundary. By comparison, the MFS does not present these difficulties, making the modeling process simpler [28]. According to Godinho et al. [29], and due to the usual geometry of sonic crystals, which exhibit a constant cross-section along one direction but may be excited by a 3-D source, a 2.5-D MFS formulation was used (following the works by Tadeu A, and Godinho L, and Godinho et al. [30, 31], respectively) with an Adaptive Cross Approximation (ACA) to obtain the sound pressure level attenuation for different sonic crystal noise barriers configurations. In addition to these works, in the works of Godinho et al. [12] and Veloso et al. [32] the MFS was also used to solve problems involving sonic crystal noise barriers.

In the work by Peiró-Torres et al [28], a comparative evaluation of some numerical methods was presented, with emphasis on the evaluation of their accuracy versus memory usage, to determine which is the most suitable for optimization methodologies in the design of new devices with better acoustic performance. Furthermore, according to the authors, for the computational memory parameter considering the particular case raised in the study, both BEM and MFS are the best methods for performing optimization processes and determining the acoustic performance of these periodic structures. Regarding the computational times, the results can be variable a lot, since they significantly depend on the type of implementation of the codes and the used hardware.

In the present work, the use of a novel specific granular material (porous concrete) was proposed to be used together with the sonic crystal noise barrier. Furthermore, with the aim of optimizing the insertion loss calculation, the periodicity condition was implemented in the MFS to represent the noise barrier with infinite length. Finally, porous concrete was represented using the Horoshenkov-Swift model to define the acoustic input parameters for the MFS considering more than one domain, and not simply applying the acoustic impedance of the material at the material/air interface as usually observed.

In the remaining part of this work, first, the mathematical formulation of the 2-D MFS is presented, together with the standard fundamental solutions for infinite and semi-infinite acoustic media. Next, the periodic fundamental solutions are presented, allowing to define the periodic character of the problem. Initially, the 2-D MFS model is validated by comparison with experimental results, using reduced-scale noise barrier prototypes. The infinite

periodic model is then compared with a FEM model. The granular porous material is incorporated in the MFS
 90 model using the Horoshenkov-Swift formulation, and this model is also compared with the FEM. Finally, a numerical
 study is presented, with a set of results that reveal the influence of some characteristic parameters, namely the radius
 of scatterers, the distance between the center of scatterers, the thickness of porous concrete, and the type of porous
 concrete in the performance of sonic crystal noise barriers through the analysis of insertion loss results.

2. Mathematical formulation

105 In this section, the mathematical formulation for the Method of Fundamental Solutions (MFS) will be presented.
 In addition, the semi-phenomenological model proposed by Horoshenkov and Swift [15, 16, 17, 18] to represent
 porous granular materials will also be described.

2.1. Method of Fundamental Solutions

Meshless methods have been highly developed in the last two decades and one of those that stands out for acoustic
 100 problem is the Method of Fundamental Solutions (MFS). By definition, and disregarding some exceptions, meshless
 methods do not require spatial or boundary discretization. For example, the MFS needs only points located along
 the domain boundary. These methods can use high-order interpolation functions or even use differential equation
 solution to solve the problem, which significantly increases the method's accuracy. Finally, when the MFS is used,
 it is not necessary to solve any integral, which could sometimes lead to difficulties or increased calculation times.

105 The propagation of sound within a 2D space on MFS formulation for sonic crystals noise barrier of infinite
 length can be mathematically described, in the frequency domain, by the Helmholtz partial differential equation,

$$\nabla^2 p + \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} p = - \sum_{k=1}^{NS} Q_k \delta(\mathbf{x}_k^f, \mathbf{x}), \quad (1)$$

where $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$; p is the acoustic pressure; $k = \frac{\omega}{c}$ is the wavenumber of the medium; $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular
 frequency; f is the frequency; c is the speed of sound propagation in the acoustic environment; NS is the number
 of sources in the domain; Q_k is the magnitude of existing sources \mathbf{x}_k^f located in (x_k^f, y_k^f) ; \mathbf{x} is a field point located
 110 at (x, y) ; and $\delta(\mathbf{x}_k^f, \mathbf{x})$ is the Dirac's delta generalized function.

Considering that a source point is placed in a generic propagation domain, at $\mathbf{x}_0 (x_0, y_0)$, it is possible to
 establish the fundamental solution for the incident sound pressure, for the first order derivative of pressure and
 for the normal particle velocity at a point \mathbf{x} , as suggested by Martins [33], which can be written as (assuming an
 implicit time dependence $e^{i\omega t}$):

$$\mathbf{Pressure} : G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_0) = -\frac{i}{4} H_0^{(2)}(kr), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{First\ derivative} : \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_0)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = H(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{n}) = \frac{ik}{4} H_1^{(2)}(kr) \frac{\partial r}{\partial \mathbf{n}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{Velocity} : \frac{i}{\rho\omega} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_0)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \frac{i}{\rho\omega} H(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{n}) = -\frac{1}{4\rho c} H_1^{(2)}(kr) \frac{\partial r}{\partial \mathbf{n}}, \quad (4)$$

where: $r = \sqrt{(x - x_0)^2 + (y - y_0)^2}$, $H_n^{(2)}(..)$ Hankel function of the second kind of integer order n , and $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

The MFS can be used to calculate the response in the ω frequency domain. According to the works of God-
 inho et al [29, 12], the solution is obtained with a linear combination of fundamental solutions, using several virtual

sources NVS, with amplitude A_l (with $l = 1, \dots, NVS$). These virtual sources are placed outside the domain of interest (i.e., in the case of acoustic barriers, inside the elements of the barrier, since the propagation occurs outside). Thus, the pressure field can be calculated as:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{l=1}^{NVS} [A_l G(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x})] + P_{inc}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (5)$$

where A_l are the unknown amplitudes of the virtual sources, which will be calculated by imposing boundary conditions and G is the fundamental solution at the point \mathbf{x} for the virtual sources located in \mathbf{x}_l^v . $P_{inc}(\mathbf{x})$ represents an incident pressure field generated by sound sources present within the domain. In many cases, when the MFS is used, an equal number of collocation points and virtual sources are considered, resulting in a generated system of equations ($NVS \times NVS$). A generic domain is schematically described below in Figure 1.

The boundary conditions for the problem (considering a generic point \mathbf{x} in the boundary Γ) are given by:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = k_d \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma, \text{ (Dirichlet condition)} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial p(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = k_n \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma, \text{ (Neumann condition)} \quad (7)$$

$$B_1 p(\mathbf{x}) + B_2 \frac{\partial p(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = k_r \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in \Gamma, \text{ (Robin condition)}, \quad (8)$$

where k_d , k_n , and k_r are arbitrary constants that can be used in acoustic problems to set the values of pressure, particle velocity, and impedance, respectively; and B_1 and B_2 are constants defined according to the Robin condition.

Figure 1: Schematic definition of the collocation points and the virtual sources applied to sonic crystals acoustic barriers.

Figure 1 shows a reduced-scale acoustic barrier prototype. By zooming in on some scatterers, it is possible to visualize the collocation points in black and the virtual sources in blue. In this figure, the collocation points are positioned on the rigid boundary of the sonic crystals noise barrier, while the virtual sources are positioned outside the analysis domain, in this case within the rigid boundary.

This system of equations is formed by prescribing, at each collocation point \mathbf{x}_m , along the limits of the barrier elements, the correct boundary conditions according to Equations (6), (7) and (8). Applying this procedure, the following equations are obtained:

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\text{NVS}} A_l \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x}_m)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = -\frac{\partial P_{inc}(\mathbf{x}_m)}{\partial \mathbf{n}}, \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^{\text{NVS}} A_l G(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x}_m) + P_{inc}(x_m) = i \frac{Z(\mathbf{x}_m)}{\rho \omega} \left(\sum_{l=1}^{\text{NVS}} A_l \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x}_m)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} + \frac{\partial P_{inc}(\mathbf{x}_m)}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \right). \quad (10)$$

where Z is a surface impedance and is given by

$$Z = \frac{p(\mathbf{x})}{\frac{i}{\rho \omega} \frac{\partial p(\mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{n}}} \left[\frac{\text{Ns}}{\text{m}^3} \right]. \quad (11)$$

From a practical point of view, this impedance can be determined from the α sound absorption coefficient of a given material. This relation between α and Z is given by

$$Z = \rho c \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha}}{1 - \sqrt{1 - \alpha}}. \quad (12)$$

Equation 9 describes the case of rigid surfaces, while Equation 10 is employed if required to assign absorption on the model surfaces. For both cases, a resulting NVS \times NVS system of equation is obtained, which allows obtaining later the acoustic pressure at any point in the domain by Equation 5.

2.1.1. MFS extension for problems with more than one region

The formulation previously described allows the analysis of acoustic problems in which there is a domain with multiple scatterers located inside. However, the formulation presented does not allow to analyze some other situations of interest, namely those that correspond to problems with multiple sub-regions or with open elements with thin walls, instead of rigid scatterers.

In Figure 2 the domain Ω is divided into two sub-domains Ω_1 and Ω_2 , the interface between them corresponding to a virtual interface created just to model the transition from air to the absorbent material.

Figure 2: Schematic definition of the collocation points and the virtual sources applied to sonic crystals acoustic barriers covered by porous concrete absorbent material.

Figure 2 shows a reduced-scale acoustic barrier prototype. By zooming in on some scatterers, it is possible to visualize two sets of collocation points in black and three sets of virtual sources in blue, red, and yellow. In this figure, the first set of collocation points is positioned on the rigid boundary of the sonic crystals noise barrier while the second set of collocation points is positioned on the interface between air and concrete material, while the virtual sources are positioned outside the analysis domain, in this case within the rigid boundary. In the case of virtual sources, the first set of these sources is located inside the rigid boundary and is responsible for the acoustic propagation in the domain Ω_2 , while the second set of virtual sources is positioned internally to the concrete/air interface and represents the acoustic propagation in the domain Ω_1 . Finally, the third set of virtual sources is positioned outside the concrete/air interface and represents the acoustic propagation in the domain Ω_2 .

Considering Figure 2, it is now necessary to define three sets of virtual sources, each containing NVS virtual sources, which will simulate, respectively, the pressure fields in the outer subdomain, Ω_1 , and in the inner subdomain, Ω_2 , and given by

$$p(\mathbf{x}, k) = \sum_{l=1}^{NVS} [A_{2,l}G(\mathbf{x}_{2,l}^v, \mathbf{x}, k_1)] + P_{inc}(\mathbf{x}) \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_1, \quad (13)$$

$$p(\mathbf{x}, k) = \sum_{l=1}^{NVS} ([A_{1,l}G(\mathbf{x}_{1,l}^v, \mathbf{x}, k_2)] + [A_{3,l}G(\mathbf{x}_{3,l}^v, \mathbf{x}, k_2)]) \text{ for } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_2. \quad (14)$$

where $A_{1,l}$, $A_{2,l}$ and $A_{3,l}$ are the amplitudes of each of the sets of virtual sources, initially unknown. To allow the resolution of this problem, it is also necessary to impose the appropriate boundary conditions, along the real boundary and the virtual interface boundary. In the case of the first, along Γ_r , those conditions correspond to

prescribing by particle velocity equal to zero according to the normal direction to the boundary (imposed either in Ω_1 or Ω_2), while in the second, along Γ_v , it is necessary to impose the continuity of the pressure field and the particle velocity field in the normal direction to the virtual boundary (between Ω_1 and Ω_2).

Thus, considering NC1 collocation points distributed in Γ_r , and NC2 collocation points distributed Γ_v , in such a way that $\text{NC1} + \text{NC2} = \text{NS}$, allows the formation of a system of 2NS equations with 2NS unknowns.

2.2. Method of Fundamental Solutions for an infinite periodic system

Herein, the interest is focused on the analysis of scattering by infinite sets of elements of a sonic crystals acoustic barrier. For this scenario, using the fundamental solution described in Equation (2) leads to the need to model each of the scatterers (or set of scatterers) using MFS, distributing collocation points and virtual sources associated with each scatterer. To accurately simulate an infinite array, it would be necessary to consider many scatterers to avoid diffraction effects that should not occur for an infinite array.

Considering a problem with a periodic array of scatterers, excited either by a periodic set of 2D point sources or by a plane wave normal to the array infinite side, the acoustic field must also exhibit the same periodicity. Based on these assumptions, if a periodicity a is assumed, along the development direction of the infinite barrier, this means that

$$p(\mathbf{x}_{n \times a}) = p(\mathbf{x}), \text{ with } \mathbf{x} = (x, y, z) \text{ and } \mathbf{x}_{n \times a} = (x, y + n \times a, z). \quad (15)$$

In addition, and considering a purely periodic system, the position of each virtual source inside scatterer i (with i being an integer ranging from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$), can be written as,

$$\mathbf{x}_{l,i}^v = (x_l^v, y_l^v + i \times a, z_l^v). \quad (16)$$

Given these previous assumptions, if a set of NVSi virtual sources and collocation points is used for each scatterer i , and the amplitudes of each virtual source located at $x_{l,i}^v$, are given by $A_{l,i}$, then

$$A_{l,-\infty} = \dots = A_{l,-1} = A_{l,0} = A_{l,1} = \dots = A_{l,\infty} = A_l. \quad (17)$$

Thus, the pressure field at any point \mathbf{x} in the propagation domain $p(\mathbf{x})$, must have the same periodicity as the system, and it can also be written as:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{l=1}^{NVS_i} \left(A_l \sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} G_h(\mathbf{x}_{l,i}^v, \mathbf{x}) \right) + P_{inc}^{per}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (18)$$

In addition, for this analysis as an infinite periodic structure, with periodicity a along the y axis, and defining the same periodicity as the physical system, this problem can be solved considering an adapted fundamental solution for the MFS. Thus, a possible fundamental solution for this case can be written as

$$G_{per}(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} G(\mathbf{x}_{l,i}^v, \mathbf{x}) \text{ with } \mathbf{x}_{l,i}^v = (x_l^v, y_l^v + i \times a, z_l^v). \quad (19)$$

Although, (Equation 19) can indeed be used as the basis of a periodic MFS formulation, it should be noted that the involved summation can pose convergence problems, and also requires a very large number of terms to converge, thus leading to very long computational times. However, at this point, Equation (19) just represents an infinite summation of periodically placed sources along one direction. According to Tadeu and Godinho [30], and Godinho et al. [34], the Green's function (i.e. fundamental solution) can be represented as a sum of 2D sources with axial variation of the wavenumbers as

$$G(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}) = -\frac{i}{8\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} H_0^{(2)}(k'r') e^{-ik_y(y-y_0)} dk_y, \quad (20)$$

where $k' = \sqrt{(\frac{\omega}{c})^2 - k_y^2}$ (with $\text{imag}(k') < 0$), and $r' = |x - x_0|$. Discretizing this integral in regular intervals of dk_y , one obtains the acoustic field in the form of an infinite summation as

$$G(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}) = -\frac{i}{8\pi} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} H_0^{(2)}(k'r') e^{-i \times k_y \times n \times (y-y_0)} \times dk_y, \quad (21)$$

It should be noted that this type of approach, described in [12], has also been addressed by Linton [35], [36].

According to Chen et al. [37, 38], the introduction of such discretization is equivalent to consider a set of point sources equally spaced from L along the periodicity axis, such that $dk_y = \frac{2\pi}{L}$, then Equation (21) is rewritten as

$$-\frac{i}{8\pi} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} H_0^{(2)}(k'r') e^{-i \times \frac{2\pi}{L} \times n \times (y-y_0)} \times \frac{2\pi}{L} = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} G(\mathbf{x}_{l,i}^v, \mathbf{x}). \quad (22)$$

Therefore, if $L = a$,

$$G_{per}(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} G(\mathbf{x}_{l,i}^v, \mathbf{x}) = -\frac{i}{4a} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} H_0^{(2)}(k'r') e^{-i \times \frac{2\pi}{a} \times n \times (y-y_0)}, \quad (23)$$

where a is a distance between center of scatterers. The technique of using a periodic function can also be applied to the derivative of the Green's function, which can be seen as

$$\frac{\partial G_{per}(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{n}}, \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_{i=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}_l^v, \mathbf{x})}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = -\frac{i}{4\pi} \sum_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left(k' H_1^{(2)}(k'r') e^{-i \times \frac{2\pi}{a} \times n \times (y-y_0)} \frac{\partial r'}{\partial \mathbf{n}} + H_0^{(2)}(k'r') \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \left(e^{-i \times \frac{2\pi}{a} \times n \times (y-y_0)} \right) \right). \quad (25)$$

2.3. Porous Concrete fluid equivalent estimation

Porous materials are composed of two phases, one solid (skeleton) and the other fluid. Acoustic dissipation within porous materials occurs due to the interaction between the solid and the fluid phases [39, 40], being these losses viscous and/or thermal. The interest in developing porous concrete solutions for external passive noise treatment increased in the last years because these materials can be used in external environments, even without protection against environmental agents and structural reinforcement.

In porous concrete materials, the granules (aggregates) are usually distributed differently from the fibers by following a log-normal pore distribution, resulting in smaller porosity and higher tortuosity [18]. The sound absorption coefficient of porous concrete materials depends on the porous size, the sample thickness and the water-cement ratio.

The Horoshenkov-Swift model [41] considers four macroscopic parameters, namely, air flow resistivity, σ , open porosity, ϕ , tortuosity, α_∞ , and the pore size standard deviation, σ_p . The fluid equivalent properties, complex density, $\tilde{\rho}$, and complex compressibility, \tilde{C} , respectively, can be calculated using the following equations:

$$\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}} = \frac{\alpha_\infty}{\phi} \left(\rho_0 - i \frac{\phi \sigma}{\omega \alpha_\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\omega) \right), \quad (26)$$

$$\tilde{C}_{\text{eq}} = \frac{\phi}{\gamma P_0} \left(\gamma - \frac{\rho_0(\gamma - 1)}{\rho_0 - i \frac{\sigma \phi}{\omega \alpha_\infty N_{Pr}} \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(N_{Pr} \omega)} \right). \quad (27)$$

The term γ is the ratio of specific heats, P_0 is the atmospheric pressure, and N_{Pr} is the Prandtl number, and $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\omega)$ is the viscosity correction function, which can be presented in the form of a Padé approximation as:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\omega) = \frac{1 + a_1 \epsilon + a_2 \epsilon^2}{1 + b_1 \epsilon}, \quad (28)$$

Here, the term $\epsilon = \sqrt{i \frac{\omega \rho_0 \alpha_\infty}{\sigma \phi}}$ is a dimensionless parameter $a_1 = \frac{\theta_1}{\theta_2}$, $a_2 = \theta_1$, $b_1 = a_1$. The terms θ_1 and θ_2 are pore shape factors defined by the porous geometry. When a circular pore shape is assumed, $\xi = [\sigma_p \ln(2)]^2$, two asymptotic expansion coefficients can be obtained by,

$$\theta_1 = \left(\frac{4}{3} \right) e^{4\xi} - 1, \quad (29)$$

$$\theta_2 = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \right) e^{\frac{3}{2}\xi}. \quad (30)$$

The characteristic impedance and the wavenumber of the material are given, respectively, by:

$$\tilde{Z}_c = \sqrt{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}} \tilde{K}_{\text{eq}}}, \quad (31)$$

$$\tilde{k}_c = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}}{\tilde{K}_{\text{eq}}}}. \quad (32)$$

where $\tilde{\rho}_{\text{eq}}$ is the complex density, \tilde{K}_{eq} is the bulk modulus, and $\tilde{K}_{\text{eq}} = 1/\tilde{C}_{\text{eq}}$.

3. Numerical model verification and experimental

validation

This section will present the experimental validation of the MFS models, considering rigid acoustic barriers, and a numerical verification based on Finite Element Methods simulation for the infinite periodic MFS with and without porous concrete materials covering the sonic crystals. In addition, the macroscopic parameters used for porous concrete fluid equivalent representation throughout the Horoshenkov-Swift model will be described.

215 *3.1. Experimental validation of the numerical model*

In this subsection, the validation of the traditional MFS numerical model will be presented, also describing the entire setup used in the experimental measurements and the reduced scale prototype configurations used.

3.1.1. Experimental setup

220 In order to approach free field conditions, the experimental validation work was carried out in a semi-anechoic/anechoic chamber from the Department of Civil Engineering at the University of Coimbra, based on ISO 10847 [4] and EN 1793-6 [42] standards.

225 In this way, the measurement setup for experimental evaluation is shown in Figure 3. The Insertion Loss (IL) provided by the noise barrier was evaluated using a signal analyzer, Symphonie model 01dB-Metrovib, with the software dB Bati 32, a microphone and preamp G.R.A.S Sound & Vibration, respectively, model 40AF, and model 26AK, 1/2", a signal strength amplifier InterM, model M700, and an Alpha - 100 RTO sound source.

Figure 3: Prototype of the acoustic barrier formed by sonic crystals, in reduced scale (1: 6), tested in the laboratory anechoic condition.

3.1.2. Experimental validation of the traditional MFS model considering rigid barriers

230 For the experimental validation of the numerical model presented in Section 2.1, a finite acoustic barrier based on sonic crystals on a reduced scale (1:6) was used. The acoustic barrier was made using Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC) tubes, with a diameter of circular elements (d) of 2 cm and a distance between centers of these circular elements (a) of 3.4 cm; the tubes were placed between two panels of extruded polystyrene (XPS) to remain in the desired position, in terms of verticality and spacing between scatterers.

The experimental test was carried out in a semi-anechoic chamber where it was necessary to place absorbent material in the floor to avoid reflections in this plane and simulate the free field condition. In Figure 4, a test setup

scheme can seen for the experiment with the positioning of the test sample, speaker and microphone adapted from
 235 the above mentioned standard.

Figure 4: Assembly scheme of the experiment carried out.

In Figure 4, h_B is the barrier height, h_s is the reference height ($0.5 h_B$), t_b is the barrier thickness, d_s is the horizontal distance from loudspeaker to barrier, d_M is the horizontal distance from centre microphone to barrier and s is the distance between the microphones.

For the validation, four experimental configurations were tested, changing the number of columns of the barrier and the distance between the centers of the sonic crystal noise barrier elements. The configurations used are
 240 summarized and illustrated in Table 1 and in Figure 5.

Parameters	First configuration	Second configuration	Third configuration	Fourth configuration
L (cm)	100	100	100	100
a (cm)	2.83	3.34	2.83	3.34
N	3	3	4	4
G_d	rectangular	rectangular	rectangular	rectangular

Table 1: Constituent parameters of the acoustic barrier.

In this table L is the barrier length, a is the distance between centers of the circular elements of the sonic crystal noise barrier, N the number of columns of barrier and G_d is the type of geometric distribution of elements of barrier.

In Figure 5 it is possible to observe one of four configurations analyzed using the MFS. In this figure it is possible
 245 to note the sound source (monopole), nine measurement points, the collocation points in red and the virtual sources in blue. From the laboratory tests, it was possible to validate the numerical model previously presented. In Figure 6

Figure 5: Scheme of sonic crystals noise barrier with 3 columns of circular elements, with rectangular spatial distribution and 100 cm in length.

the comparisons between the numerical results and experimental data are observed for the noise barriers formed by circular elements with a equal to 3.34 cm, for 3 and 4 columns, and a equal to 2.84 cm, for 3 and 4 columns, respectively.

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Figure 6: Comparison between the MFS results and experimental data of IL for an acoustic barrier formed by sonic crystals: a) result for a barrier with 3 columns and a spacing between centers of the barrier elements of 2.84 cm; b) result for a barrier with 4 columns and a spacing between centers of the barrier elements of 2.84 cm; c) result for a barrier with 3 columns and a spacing between centers of the barrier elements of 3.34 cm; d) result for a barrier with 4 columns and a spacing between centers of the barrier elements of 3.34 cm.

250 Analyzing the results presented in Figure 6 it is clear that the [agreement](#) between numerical and experimental results is satisfactory, in general, with the global trend of the insertion loss curves being quite similar for both approaches (numerical and experimental). For all 4 sets of results, it is observed that the bandgap was well represented and the amplitude of the insertion loss showed very close values when the two results were compared. In addition, numerical and experimental results have the same trend across all frequency spectra.

255 In relation to the small differences in the insertion loss amplitude values, it is believed that these occur due to the experimental conditions and the difference between the numerical and experimental approaches since the first was represented by a 2-D model, where the barrier has infinite height, while, in the prototype used in the experimental test, the barrier has finite height. On the other hand, the due influence of the sound source used may exist, since the numerical model used a monopole (point source) while in the experimental test a speaker with directivity different from that of a monopole was adapted.
260

3.2. Numerical verification of the MFS model

3.2.1. Numerical verification of the infinite periodic MFS model considering rigid barriers

After the experimental validation of the traditional MFS model using reduced scale prototypes, the infinite periodic MFS is used in order to perform all analyses with a lower computational cost, being this model verified by
265 comparison with classic FEM formulation [40, 43, 44, 45].

A square lattice geometric distribution was considered, using three columns and a periodicity/distance between the center of the circular elements of the acoustic barrier (a) equal to 17 cm and the radius of the circular elements

equal to 6 cm. The configuration used in FEM simulation (which can be represented in Figure 7) consists of representing only one line of the elements of the sonic crystal acoustic barrier.

Figure 7: Configuration used in the FEM model for numerical verification purposes.

270 In Figure 7, it can be seen that the FEM model (implemented by the authors using MatLab software) was represented by a rectangle, where particle velocity ($v = 1$) was imposed on the left boundary represented by plane waves, rigid wall boundary conditions ($v = 0$) were imposed on the upper and lower boundaries of the rectangle domain, and on the walls of the circular elements of the barrier, in addition to imposing, at the left and right end of the rectangle, an impedance condition ($Z = \rho_0 c_0$), where ρ_0 is the air density and c_0 is the sound velocity in the

275 air. When using these boundary conditions, in the 2-D FEM simulations only one row of the infinite length noise barrier is being simulated, which is composed of 3 infinite height scatterers. In this way, it is possible to simulate a periodic 2-D configuration, since these boundary conditions indeed correspond to the conditions of periodicity along the y-axis for normal incidence and a symmetric system. As for the mesh used, triangular elements with a maximum length of its sides equal to 2 cm were used (8 elements per wavelength were used for a frequency of 2kHz).

280 To evaluate the IL of the sonic crystal acoustic barrier, two lines of receivers placed after the inclusions were used. The result obtained through the FEM was used to verify the result of the infinite periodic MFS model. The comparison between the results of infinite periodic FEM, the infinite periodic MFS, and the finite MFS can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Comparison of IL results for the sonic crystal noise barrier using the infinite FEM model, infinite periodic MFS, and finite MFS approaches.

In Figure 8, it is possible to observe that both approaches (FEM, infinite periodic MFS and finite MFS) present, in general, a satisfactory representation of the insertion loss for a sonic crystal noise barrier. Comparing only the periodic and infinite MFS models with the finite MFS it is possible to observe some small differences that occur due to the diffraction effect occurring at the extreme scatterers of the finite sonic crystal barrier. However, in all numerical models it is possible to observe that the bandgap is well represented, with the IL amplitude values presenting the same order of magnitude when analyzing the first peak and a little difference for the second peak.

3.2.2. Verification of the MFS model for noise barriers covered by porous materials

In this subsection, the verification of the MFS model applied to the sonic crystals noise barriers covered by porous concrete will be presented. For this verification, the FEM model will be used similarly to what was done in the previous section. The present FEM model differs from the previously described one due to the addition of porous concrete covering the rigid wall of the scatterers.

To evaluate the use of porous concrete applied to sonic crystal noise barriers in order to mitigate road traffic noise, an equivalent fluid representation was used in conjunction with the MFS model. This approach will represent porous concrete using the Horoshenkov-Swift model to define the complex properties of the absorbent material. In Figure 3.2.2A, it is possible to see a schematic representation of the infinite periodic MFS model used to represent the sonic crystals noise barriers with porous concrete. Figure 3.2.2B shows the value of the external radius (r_2) was set equal to 6 cm and the thickness of the porous material was variable (e), the internal radius (r_1) being given by $r_1 = r_2 - e$. In this model, two types of boundaries were considered, the first being rigid and the other an interface where conditions of continuity of pressure and particle velocity were imposed between the Ω_1 and Ω_2 domains.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of the assembly of the MFS model: A) considering a periodic and infinity configuration; B) considering noise barrier sonic crystals covered by porous concrete.

As stated before, the porous concrete will be represented as fluid equivalent using the equations presented in Section 2.3. The four macroscopic parameters used to describe the porous concrete made with expanded clay aggregates were previously obtained by the authors [18], being these parameters obtained through the inverse method [46], except the open porosity which was experimentally characterized. These parameters are presented in Table 2.

Material	σ [Ns/m^4]	ϕ	α_∞	σ_d
Porous concrete (M2)	3896.06	0.46	1.89	0.25
Porous concrete (M3)	7171.53	0.36	2.73	0.41

Table 2: Macroscopic parameters of the porous material. M2 and M3 are designated porous concrete mixtures from the original work [18].

Here, the M2 mixture was assumed to cover the sonic crystal noise barriers elements and this configuration was simulated using the infinite periodic MFS model as illustrated in Figure 3.2.2. This model was validated using the FEM model as in the previous section. The only difference between the FEM model with and without porous concrete is that in the last one, a region with thickness $e = 2$ cm with finer discretization was created where the equivalent fluid properties obtained through the Horoshenkov-Swift model were assumed (similar to Figure 3.2.2) and this result can be seen in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Comparison of IL results for the sonic crystal acoustic barrier covered by porous concrete using the FEM and infinite periodic MFS approaches.

Figure 10 shows the comparison of the results of the insertion loss of sonic crystal noise barriers covered by 2 cm of porous concrete (mixture M2) using the infinite periodic MFS model and the FEM model. In this figure, it is possible to observe that results from both models are almost coincident throughout the analyzed frequency spectrum and, in addition, the bandgap is very well represented in both approaches. Thus, it is possible to state that the infinite periodic MFS model has been satisfactorily verified.

4. Numerical results for cylinders coated with porous concrete

In this section, the results of numerical tests using a noise barrier coated with porous concrete will be presented and analyzed. In these numerical examples, two types of porous concrete will be evaluated, as well as different thicknesses of these materials and different scatterers radii covered by porous concrete to obtain a larger bandgap.

In Figures 11 and 12 it is possible to observe the influence of both the flow resistivity and porosity of porous concrete parameters for the results of the insertion loss of an acoustic barrier covered with porous concrete. To carry out the analyses, the M3 concrete mix was chosen, with a thickness of 4 cm of porous concrete, and keeping the external radius equal to 6 cm to ensure that the first bandgap occurs at approximately the same frequency when compared to the noise barrier without absorbent concrete mix cover. To assess the influence of flow resistivity, this parameter was varied from $4000 \frac{Ns}{m^4}$ to $38000 \frac{Ns}{m^4}$. These limiting values were chosen since $4000 \frac{Ns}{m^4}$ is approximately the lowest σ value (M2 concrete mixture) tested experimentally by Pereira et al.[18] and the value $38000 \frac{Ns}{m^4}$ represents the average flow resistivity of medium density fiberglass. For porosity, the same procedure was performed, with the porosity varying from 0.36, the lowest ϕ value (M3 concrete mixture) tested experimentally by Pereira et al.[18] up to 0.9 which represents the average porosity value for medium density fiberglass.

Figure 11: Evaluation of the influence of the flow resistivity (σ) porous concrete parameter on the result of the insertion loss for a noise barrier covered with porous concrete. The blank region in this result is out of range.

Analyzing Figure 11, it can be observed that the first and second bandgaps are well-defined for lower values of flow resistivity. However, as this σ value increases, the first and the second bandgaps join together in the frequency range, showing that this would be an interesting scenario, where there is a much wider bandgap than in rigid acoustic barriers. The blank region in this result represents out-of-range values, which exceed the limits of the color plot in terms of insertion loss values for the flow resistivity values used. For very high values of flow resistivity, the IL may reveal that the two bandgaps became separated again, leading to a result close to the expected for rigid scatterers with a radius equal to the external radius of the modeled scatterers.

Figure 12: Evaluation of the influence of the porosity (ϕ) porous concrete parameter on the result of the insertion loss for an acoustic barrier covered with porous concrete. The blank region in this result is out of range.

340 Analyzing Figure 12, it can be observed that the first and second bandgaps are again clearly visible for lower porosity values. However, for values of $\phi \approx 0.8$, there is a combination of the first and the second bandgaps along the frequency range, showing that this would be an interesting scenario, where there is a much larger bandgap than conventional sonic crystals noise barriers. As above, the blank region in this result is out of range.

Following this initial analysis, the influence of the two types of porous concrete mixtures (M2 and M3) on the performance of sonic crystal noise barriers will be evaluated. Furthermore, for the material with the best acoustic performance together with the barrier, the influence of the variation of the external radius of the noise barrier on the insertion loss results will be evaluated. The first set of results corresponds to the evaluation of two porous concretes with macroscopic parameters that can be seen in Table 2, covering the sonic crystals scatterers. Figure 13 shows the comparison of IL curves using M2 and M3 porous concrete mixtures with a thickness equal to 4 cm external radius equal to 6 cm and internal radius equal to 2 cm.

Figure 13: Comparison of IL results for sonic crystal barriers covered with M2 and M3 porous concrete mixtures.

In Figure 13, the behavior of the noise barrier covered by the M2 and M3 concrete mixtures can be observed. Evaluating these results, it can be observed that, for both materials, there is a decrease in the magnitude of the IL at the first bandgap. Additionally, for frequencies in which rigid scatterers provide almost no attenuation, a significant increase in acoustic performance can be achieved, due to the absorbent characteristics of the porous concrete material. Furthermore, when analyzing these results, it is possible to conclude that, in general, the M3 concrete mixture together with the sonic crystal noise barrier performs better than the M2 concrete mixture.

To discuss the effect of the covering material thickness in the insertion loss provided by their structures, additional numerical simulations were made. In order to establish a better comparison of the influence of M2 and M3 porous concrete mixtures on the curves of insertion loss of the acoustic barriers, the IL was evaluated (shown in Figure 14) as a function of the thickness of the porous concrete layer, considering a constant value for the external radius of 6 cm.

Figure 14: Comparison of IL results for noise barrier sonic crystal barriers covered by porous concrete for different porous concrete layer thicknesses considering: A) M2 porous concrete mixture; B) M3 porous concrete mixtures.

Observing the results presented in Figure 14, it can be seen that as the thickness of the layer of granular material increases, there is a decrease in the magnitude of the first bandgap and the typical sonic crystal behavior becomes less evident. However, for frequencies higher than the first bandgap there is a clear increase in the IL values. For thicknesses greater than 4 cm, using the M3 concrete mixture, significant IL values for the first bandgap are registered, and also in the region between the first and second bandgaps the IL value is significantly increased, almost leading to a single much wider bandgap along the frequency range.

Following the evaluation of the type of porous concrete (M2 and M3 mixture), it is useful to determine a way to obtain a wider bandgap. For this purpose, the Bragg's frequency was changed, given by $f = \frac{c}{2a}$, and values for the lattice constant of $a = 17$ cm, $a = 19$ cm and $a = 21$ cm were tested. To obtain the new values of a , the external radius of the scatterers was increased (from 6 cm to 7 cm and 8 cm), making the bandgap to move to slightly lower frequencies and looking for a porous concrete thickness that provides maximum absorption at frequencies above the new bandgap. The result of this evaluation can be seen in Figures 15 and 16, where scatterers with external radii equal to 7 and 8 cm, and porous concrete thickness equal to 2, 3, 4, and 5 cm, respectively, were simulated.

Figure 15: IL evaluation for sonic crystal barriers (scatterers radius equal to 7 cm) covered with different thicknesses of the M3 porous concrete mixture.

Figure 16: IL evaluation for sonic crystal barriers (scatterers radius equal to 8 cm) covered with different thicknesses of the M3 porous concrete mixture.

375 Analyzing the results presented in Figures 15 and 16 it can be observed that, for all concrete material thicknesses, there is a decrease in the magnitude of IL in the first bandgap. Furthermore, it is possible to observe that there is a slight displacement of the first bandgap to lower frequencies. In these results, it was also observed that for all porous concrete thicknesses (M3) tested, there was an increase in insertion loss for frequencies above those of the first bandgap. However, when analyzing the performance of the acoustic barrier with external radius equal to 7 and
 380 8 cm in conjunction with the M3 porous concrete mixture, it was observed that for the 5 cm thickness of porous

concrete, a slight decrease in the magnitude of the first bandgap occurs, but it is possible to visualize a significant increase in IL right after the bandgap for both configurations (scatterers with radius equal to 7 and 8 cm), thus obtaining a single wider bandgap.

The effect of creating the wider bandgap was due to the increase in the external radius of the scatterers, causing a decrease in the Bragg's frequency, which shifts the first bandgap to lower frequencies, together with the use of a porous concrete thickness that has maximum sound absorption around 1200 Hz.

5. Final remarks

In the present paper, the authors presented an approach for the analysis of 2D acoustic problems with infinite periodicity along one direction, making use of the MFS. The proposed method has been developed in order to allow dealing with sonic crystals made of 2D scatterers, infinitely repeated with constant spacing along one direction, with efficiency. It should be pointed out that the proposed approach allows for overcoming some significant drawbacks identified for the MFS, avoiding the full discretization of a large number of scatterers, thus reducing the problem size and computational costs.

Furthermore, the authors have used the MFS model to analyze the performance of sonic crystal acoustic barriers using absorbent materials to cover the structural elements. The chosen absorbent material was porous concrete, as it is easy to install and does not present inherent problems to exposure to climate agents, like foams and fibers. In this work, it was chosen to model the porous concrete using the Horoshenkov-Swift model and to incorporate its properties in the periodic and infinite MFS.

The models presented in this work were validated and verified in different stages. Initially, the finite MFS was validated by comparing it with an experiment using a small-scale sonic crystal acoustic barrier. In the sequence, the periodic and infinite MFS model was verified against a FEM model and both models were compared with the finite MFS model for a large-length barrier. Finally, porous concrete was incorporated as equivalent fluid material into the MFS model and this was verified by comparison with a FEM model where the properties of porous concrete were also incorporated.

Finally, some numerical application examples were analyzed in order to obtain a better performance of the sonic crystals acoustic barriers covered by porous concrete. In the configurations evaluated, it was possible to observe a dependence of the performance with respect to porous concrete mixture properties. Furthermore, the effect of varying the radius of the sonic barrier elements covered by porous concrete was evaluated. This analysis showed good results because when there are small thicknesses of absorbent material, the sonic crystal effect is preserved and the IL is still slightly increased at frequencies higher than the bandgap. For the thickness of 5 cm, for both concrete mixtures analyzed it was possible to observe that the bandgap magnitude decreases slightly, however in frequencies above the bandgap there is a significant increase in IL, thus obtaining a much wider bandgap than before. The presented results are seen to be very promising for the future development and implementation of practical solutions for sonic crystal acoustic barriers.

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